

RESIN PRESSURE AND RESIN FLOW INSIDE A COMPOSITE JOINT DURING THERMAL EXPANSION PROCESS

Weibo Zhang¹, Xuhao Liang², Min Li^{1*}, Yizhuo Gu¹, Shaokai Wang¹, Zuoguang Zhang¹

¹ Key Laboratory of Aerospace Advanced Materials and Performance (Ministry of Education), School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University
No. 37 Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing 100191, China

² Shanghai Composite Science and Technique Company Limited
No. 3636 Zhaolou Road, Minhang District, Shanghai 201112, China

*Corresponding Author: Min Li, Email: leemy@buaa.edu.cn

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ABSTRACT

Thermal expansion process is widely used for manufacturing carbon fiber composite products with box, tube shape and multi-cavity structure. The compacting pressure on prepreg stack is generated by core mold with high thermal expansion coefficient inside a closed mold, which is balanced by resin pressure inside prepreg stack and the effective stress of fiber bed. Resin pressure is one of the most important parameters for controlling the quality of composite, which significantly influences resin flow and defect formation. In this study, resin pressures inside a carbon fiber composite joint during thermal expansion process with R10301 silicone rubber core mold and Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold were measured by means of a self-developed resin pressure online monitoring system. And resin flow at different positions of the composite joint was analyzed according to the resin pressure variation. Besides, fiber volume fraction and porosity of different positions were investigated through micrographs to evaluate the quality of the joint. The experimental results demonstrate that the online monitoring system can well meet the requirement for measuring resin pressure inside the prepreg before gelation. The resin pressure profiles of the composite joints processed with R10301 silicone rubber core mold and Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold are significantly different, which are greatly influenced by thermal expansion coefficient, bulk elastic modulus of the silicone rubber core mold and the process gap. On the other hand, the resin pressure at the corner area is much lower than those at other areas, resulting in voids and resin-rich defects. These results provide a basic understanding on the resin pressure characteristic inside the composite joint during thermal expansion process and a direct guidance for process optimization to improve the quality of composite product.

1 INTRODUCTION

Molding pressure is one of the most important parameters in manufacturing resin matrix composite, which has a great impact on the quality of products. The applied pressure source for most of composite manufacturing processes is external, such as autoclave process, hot pressing process, and vacuum assistant resin infusion process. For manufacturing the composite parts with box-shaped, tube-shaped or multi-cavity structure, this pressure mode will often cause the problems that the external pressure cannot be effectively applied to the composite and the pressure distribution on composite is uneven, in consequence the quality of products cannot satisfy the manufacturing requirements. Nevertheless, thermal expansion process relies on a core mold with a large coefficient of thermal expansion inside a closed mold to generate a uniform internal pressure to compact the prepreg, which is particularly suitable for integral forming process of the composite parts with complex geometry, such as multi-cavity structure.

For the thermal expansion process, it is essential to control the thermal expansion pressure according to core mold material properties and requirements for resin curing. G.Sala^[1] studied the elastomer tooling technology, established the elastomer pressure theory model during thermal expansion process, and pointed out the thermal expansion coefficient and bulk elastic modulus of

elastomer has a great impact on thermal expansion pressure. And the material parameters of the elastomer were adjusted by adding hollow glass beads to obtain a reasonable thermal expansion pressure. Kim^[2] et al. studied the viscoelasticity of silicone rubber and established a KWW nonlinear viscoelastic equation to predict the thermal expansion pressure. Comparing with the experimental value in both the closed mold and open mold during thermal expansion process, the predicting results of KWW nonlinear viscoelastic equation were very accurate. J.M.Richards^[3] et al. studied the thermal conductivity of silicone rubber for thermal expansion process, and improve the thermal conductivity by means of adding 25% and 30% (in volume) of carbon , carbon black and chopped carbon fibre, respectively. The results show that the addition of chopped carbon fibre is the best effective in improving the thermal conductivity, adding 30% (in volume) chopped carbon fibre can increase the thermal conductivity of silicone rubber by 100%. F.Ernesto^[4] et al. developed the tool to control the expansion rate of silicone rubber core mold and processed the square tube with round chamfer. The experiment results demonstrated the tooling can effectively control the expansion pressure generated by silicone rubber core mold, and tubes manufactured at pressures of 0.69-1.03 MPa were of good quality and had reasonably uniform wall thicknesses.

According to the fiber compact model proposed by David^[5] and Gutowski^[6], the applied pressure during process is balanced by the resin pressure and the effective stress of the fiber bed. Resin pressure not only affects the resin flow direction and rate, but also affects the formation of voids inside composite products^[7]. In order to further reveal the effect of thermal expansion pressure on the quality of composite products, it is of great significance to study the change of resin pressure during thermal expansion process.

In this study, a composite joint of the aircraft has been processed with R10301 silicone rubber core mold and Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold, respectively. The influence of thermal expansion coefficient and bulk elastic modulus of silicone rubber core mold on the resin pressure was investigated and the resin flow inside the composite joint was analysed by online monitoring the resin pressure inside the prepreg during process. And then the quality of the composite joints processed with the two kind of silicone rubber core mold was compared. The results provide a basic understanding of the resin pressure characteristics of the parts during the thermal expansion process, which is of great reference value to the control of product quality.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Experimental raw materials

R10301 (Chengrand Research Institute of Chemical Industry CO.) and Aircast 3700 (Airtech CO.) were used as the thermally-expandable core mold, which were both liquid two-component silicone rubber vulcanized at room temperature. The material parameters of the silicone rubber were tested, and test results were shown in Table 1. The T300 carbon fiber/epoxy unidirectional prepreg, 0.17mm per layer and 50% resin content, and T300 carbon fiber/epoxy woven prepreg, 0.20mm per layer and 50% resin content, provided by Shanghai Academy of Spaceflight Technology, were used in this study.

Material parameters	R10301	Aircast 3700
Linear expansion coefficient ($\times 10^{-4}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	2.82	2.26
Bulk expansion coefficient ($\times 10^{-4}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	8.05	6.86
Bulk elastic modulus (MPa)	408.8	548.2

Table 1: Material parameters of the silicone rubber.

2.2 Process project of the composite joint

The mold for thermal expansion process mainly includes internal elastomer core mold and external rigid mold. In this study, the external rigid mold made from steel was assembled by four parts, and the

guide grooves were chiselled nearby the matching faces of each mold parts, so that the excess resin inside prepreg could be extruded into the guide grooves under the thermal expansion pressure to obtain the reasonable fiber volume fraction, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pictures of the external steel mold.

In order to limit the position of the external steel mold to ensure that the compound molds were closely mated under high thermal expansion pressure, the lock tools were set around the external steel mold, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Pictures of the lock tools.

The silicone rubber core mold is heated and expanded to generate a compaction effect on the prepreg, and the thermal expansion pressure is related to the temperature and process gap. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the expansion pressure of the core mold when heating, but also to meet the requirements for the resin curing in the prepreg when developing the temperature schedule of thermal expansion process. The process gap for cylinder section and flat region of the pedestal is 0mm and 1.2mm, respectively. After calculation, the temperature schedule was developed as Table 2. And the temperature of the external mold and silicone rubber core mold were tested by BH315-T01 temperature field acquisition system, as shown in Figure 3.

Step	Temperature control
1	Room temperature rises to $60 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, heating rate of $0.5\text{-}0.8^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{min}$
2	Holding half an hour at $60 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$
3	Rising to $90 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, heating rate of $0.5\text{-}0.8^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{min}$
4	Holding one hour at $90 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$
5	Rising to $115 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, heating rate of $0.5\text{-}0.8^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{min}$
6	Holding one hour at $115 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$
7	Rising to $130 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, heating rate of $0.5\text{-}0.8^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{min}$
8	Holding two hours at $130 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$
9	Rising to $180 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, heating rate of $0.5\text{-}0.8^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{min}$
10	Holding three hours at $180 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$

11	Cooling down to $50 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for stripping
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Table 2: Temperature schedule for manufacturing the composite joint.

Figure 3: Schematic of mold assembly with thermocouples.
1- external steel mold;2-prepreg;3-core mold;4-process gap.

2.3 Online monitoring of resin pressure inside the composite joint

The resin pressure inside the composite joint during thermal expansion process was measured by the self-developed resin pressure online monitoring system based on the principle of pressure transfer in liquid, which consists of pressure sensors, hydraulic fluid reservoirs, silicone oil, and long needles with a small diameter^[8], as shown in Figure 4. The needles were stainless steel hollow tubes with 0.8mm outer diameter (0.6mm inner diameter), which were inserted into the prepreg during process. As the size of the needles was very small, it has less influence on resin pressure and resin flow. According to Pascal's law, the resin pressure at the needle end is effectively transferred to the pressure sensor through the silicone oil in the needle and the hydraulic liquid reservoir when the resin is heated and melted into a liquid state, and the pressure data is collected in real time by the computer. When the resin becomes solid after the gel point, the resin pressure cannot be measured by this monitoring system because the principle of pressure transfer in liquid is no longer applicable^[9, 10].

Figure 4: Schematic of the resin pressure online monitoring system.

Since the external steel mold was completely closed, the small holes were drilled on the mold so that the needles could be inserted into the prepreg, as shown in Figure 5. The diameter of small holes was slightly larger than the needle, which won't cause the resin to flow out. In order to obtain the distribution of resin pressure inside the joint, the needles were embedded at the front region (position 1) and the mid region (position 2) of the cylinder, the corner region (position 3) where the cylinder and pedestal intersect, and flat region (position 4) of the pedestal, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Schematic of the needles inserted into the prepreg

Figure 6: Schematic of the positions of measuring resin pressure

2.4 Quality evaluation of the composite joint

The composite joints manufactured by thermal expansion process with different silicone rubber core mold were cut and the cross sections of position 1 to position 4 mentioned above were wet ground with successively finer silicon carbide paper and polished with diamond, and then the polished sections were observed under the optical digital microscope (Leica DM4000) to evaluate internal defects and the fiber distribution at different positions inside the joint.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Resin pressure and resin flow inside the composite joint

During the thermal expansion process, the process of prepreg compaction with the increasing temperature of the silicone rubber core mold mainly includes the following stages: (1) the silicone rubber core mold expands with the increase of temperature to fill the process gap, and it won't squeeze the prepreg until the process gap is fully filled; (2) after the process gap is fully filled, the expansion of silicone rubber core mold is limited and the prepreg begins to be compacted by the core mold when temperature continues to rise; (3) during the constant temperature stage, the expansion pressure generated by silicone rubber core mold remains unchanged; (4) at cooling stage, the silicone rubber core mold shrinkages and the expansion pressure decreases. As is well known, the process gap has a significant effect on the pressurized point and pressure value during thermal expansion process^[11]. Meanwhile, the expansion pressure is balanced by the resin pressure and the effective stress of the fiber bed. When the resin flows out of the prepreg due to extrusion by the core mold, the resin content of prepreg decreases while the fiber volume fraction rises and the fiber bed is subjected to more pressure, and in consequence the effective stress of the fiber bed increases while the resin pressure

drops immediately^[5]. Therefore, the variation of the resin content inside prepreg also affects the resin pressure significantly.

The change of resin pressure inside the joint processed with R10301 silicone rubber core mold is shown in Figure 7. The increase of resin pressure at the initial heating stage is due to compaction effect on the prepreg generated by the expansion of the silicone rubber core mold, and it can be considered that the starting point for the increase of resin pressure is the pressurized point for the prepreg. The change of the resin pressure at the initial heating stage is shown in Figure 8 more detailedly. Comparing with the pressurized point of position 1, the lag time of pressurized points of other positions is calculated, as shown in Table 3. As the size of the composite joint is small enough, the uniformity of the temperature field can be ensured when the hot press is used to heat the whole tool, so the influence of the uneven temperature distribution on the pressurized point can be neglected.

The results show that the lag of the pressurized point of position 3 and position 4 is not obvious although there is the 1.2mm process gap, while the pressurized point of position 2 lags position 1 for 216 seconds but there is no process gap at position 1 and position 2. The inapparent correlation between the lag time and the process gap is due to the two-component liquid R10301 silicone rubber with relatively high viscosity has poor fluidity, resulting in that a small amount of bubbles remain inside the silicone rubber core mold after vulcanization and the dimensional accuracy of the core mold is difficult to ensure, and then the expansion amount of core mold to fill the process gap is uneven when the prepreg begins to be compacted.

From room temperature to 60 °C, the resin pressure increases at each position and the increase rate of position 4 is the highest. In the 60 °C constant temperature stage, the temperature no longer rises, and the resin pressure of position 4 reaches the peak 0.339MPa. After that, a rapid drop occurs and the resin pressure of position 4 decreases to 0.182 MPa at the end of the 60 °C constant temperature stage. This is mainly due to that the resin is extruded from the prepreg into the guide groove of mold under high expansion pressure, resulting in the resin content decreasing at this position, and the fiber bed is subjected to more expansion pressure. The resin pressure increase rate of position 3 was significantly lower than position 4, the resin pressure reached only 0.09MPa at 60 °C, because position 3 is at the corner of the joint, the silicone rubber core mold is unable to fit tightly with the external steel mold, resulting in weak compaction of prepreg. The resin pressure trend of position 2 is similar to position 4, and the resin pressure of position 2 reaches the peak 0.173MPa in the 60 °C constant temperature stage, followed by a quick decrease. The resin pressure gradient between position 1 and position 2 drives resin to flow from position 2 to position 1, which causes that the resin pressure of position 2 has a significant drop while the resin pressure of position 1 continues to increase in the 60 °C constant temperature stage. At the end of the 60 °C constant temperature stage, the resin pressures of position 1 and position 2 are substantially equal, which is the result of the resin flow balancing resin pressure. As the temperature rises from 60 °C to 90 °C, the resin pressure rises again at each position and reaches the peak at the same time, since the silicone rubber core mold further squeezes the prepreg and the expansion pressure continues to rise with the temperature rise. Meanwhile, the viscosity of the resin decreases with increasing temperature, and the fluidity gets better. The resin pressure of each position decreases simultaneously due to the further reduction of the resin content caused by resin flowing into the guide groove. Similarly, when the temperature rises from 90 °C to 115 °C, the resin pressure rises again at each position, and then the resin pressure drops to about 0.05 MPa with increasing amount of resin outflow. Finally, the resin gels when the temperature rises to 130 °C, and the resin pressure has an abnormal increase. By this time, the principle of pressure transfer in liquid is no longer applicable to the resin pressure test, and the resin no longer flows.

Figure 7: Measured resin pressures inside the joint with R10301 silicone rubber core mold

Figure 8: Resin pressures at the initial heating stage with R10301 silicone rubber core mold

Monitoring position	Position1	Position2	Position3	Position4
Lag time (s)		216	168	100

Table 3: Pressurized point of different positions with R10301 silicone rubber core mold.

The change of resin pressure inside the joint processed with Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold is shown in Figure 9. The the resin pressure at the initial heating stage is shown in Figure 10 more detailedly. Comparing with the pressurized point of position1, the lag time of pressurized points of other positions is calculated, as shown in Table 4. The results show that the lag of the pressurized point of position 3 and position 4 is obvious since there is the 1.2mm process gap. And the pressurized point of position 1 and position 2 is completely consistent. It is shown that the correlation between the pressurized point and the process gap is significant because the liquid two-component Aircast 3700 silicone rubber with low viscosity has good fluidity, which can ensure the accuracy of the size and smooth surface during manufacturing the core mold, therefore the silicone rubber core mold expands evenly to compact the prepreg under the same process gap.

From room temperature to 60°C, the resin pressure increases at each position and the resin pressure increase rate of position 2 is the highest. In the 60 °C constant temperature stage, the resin pressure of position 2 reaches a peak of 0.693MPa followed by a rapid decrease to 0.403MPa at the end of the 60 °C constant temperature stage. The resin pressure of position 1 decreases much less than position 2 in the 60 °C constant temperature stage, and the resin pressure difference between position 1 and position 2 gradually decreases, which reduces to 0.012 MPa at the end of the 60 °C constant

temperature stage. On the one hand, the high resin pressure of position 2 drives the resin to flow from the prepreg into the guide groove. On the other hand, the resin pressure gradient between position 1 and position 2 drives the resin to flow from position 2 to position 1. Therefore, the resin content of position 2 reduces quickly resulting in a rapid decrease of resin pressure, while the resin content of position 1 changes much less than position 2 in consequence that there is just a slight drop of resin pressure of position 1. As the temperature increases, the resin viscosity decreases, the resin pressure of position 2 decreases rapidly again in 90 °C constant temperature stage, and the resin pressure of position 1 starts to decrease quickly when temperature rises to 115 °C, owing to a significant reduction of resin content inside the prepreg with the resin flowing into the guide grooves. The resin pressure of position 3 has been lower than 0.1 MPa before gel point because position 3 is at the corner of the joint, where the silicone rubber core mold is unable to fit tightly with the external steel mold so that the prepreg is unable to be compacted very well. The resin pressure of position 4 shows the similar trend with position 2, increasing rapidly at first and then having a sharp fall. This is due to the resin flows from position 4 to the guide groove and position 3 driven by the resin pressure gradient.

Figure 9: Measured resin pressures inside the joint with Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold

Figure 10: Resin pressures at the initial heating stage with Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold

Monitoring position	Position1	Position2	Position3	Position4
Lag time (s)		0	644	748

Table 4: Pressurized point of different positions with Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold.

3.2 Quality analysis through microscopic observation

To further investigate the effect of different silicone rubber core mold on the qualities of the composite joint, the micrographs were obtained, and the porosity of observed cross-section consistent with the resin pressure monitoring position was calculated, as shown in Table 5.

Monitoring position	R10301	Aircast 3700
Position 1	0.406	0.461
Position 2	0.546	0.075
Position 3	0.316	1.522
Position 4	0.084	0.322

Table 5: The porosity of observed cross-section consistent with the monitoring position.

The micrographs of the composite joint manufactured with R10301 silicone rubber core mold are shown in Figure 11 (a) ~ (d) corresponding to position 1 ~ position 4, respectively. The fiber volume fractions of position 1 and position 2 are both approximately 66%, while the fiber volume fraction of position 4 is more than 70% and the porosity was significantly lower than other positions. According to the results of online monitoring of resin pressure, the resin pressure of position 1 and position 2 is up to 0.219MPa and 0.192MPa, respectively, and decreases much less than position 4. While, the resin pressure of position 4 reaches 0.339MPa and then has a sharp fall. It demonstrates that the silicone rubber core mold generated a good compaction effect on the prepreg at position 4, but the high resin pressure drives the resin to flow out of the prepreg in a large amount, resulting in the excessive fiber volume fraction and the resin-starved areas. Position 3 is located in the corner area of the joint, where the resin pressure has been at a low level during process, although the porosity is not high, but there is a large resin-rich area with excessive resin content, mainly due to the resin flows from other areas to the corner area driven by the resin pressure gradient.

Figure 11: Micrographs of the composite joint processed with R10301 silicone rubber core mold: (a) position 1, (b) position 2, (c) position 3, (d) position 4.

The micrographs of the composite joint manufactured with Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold are shown in Figure 12 (a) ~ (d) corresponding to position 1 ~ position 4, respectively. The porosity of Position 2 is extremely low, only 0.075%, and the resin pressure reached 0.693MPa during process, indicating that the silicone rubber core mold generated a high compaction pressure on the prepreg. However, the fiber volume fraction of position 2 exceeds 70% and the substantial reduction in resin pressure indicates that the resin flows out of the prepreg in large quantities, resulting in a large resin-starved area. A large amount of voids and resin-rich are observed at position 3, where the resin pressure has been lower than 0.1MPa during process, indicating that the compaction pressure on prepreg generated by silicone rubber core mold was significantly low, and the fiber bed could not be well compacted.

Figure 12: Micrographs of the composite joint processed with Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold: (a) position 1, (b) position 2, (c) position 3, (d) position 4.

According to the porosity and fiber distribution evaluated by metallographic observation, the composite joint processed with R10301 silicone rubber core mold has low porosity and reasonable fiber volume fraction, while the compaction pressure generated by Aircast 3700 silicone rubber core mold is too high during thermal expansion process leading to fiber volume fraction of the joint far beyond a reasonable range. Therefore, R10301 silicone rubber core mold is more suitable for the production of the composite joint.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a basic understanding on the resin pressure characteristic inside the composite joint and important basis for the determination of pressurized point and resin flow during thermal expansion process. The experimental results demonstrate that resin pressure has an important effect on void formation and fiber distribution. High resin pressure indicates that the prepreg is well compacted, but it is likely to cause excessive resin flow and too high fiber volume fraction. In addition, the decrease of resin pressure can reflect the amount of resin flowing out of the prepreg. For manufacturing the composite products with complex geometries during thermal expansion process, it

is difficult to ensure that prepreg stack can be well compacted at the corner area if the elastomer core mold is unable to fit tightly with the external rigid mold. Therefore, the resin pressure is at a low level, easily leading to voids and resin-rich area. The machining accuracy and dimensional accuracy of external mold and core mold for thermal expansion process must be ensured because a small deviation on the mold dimensions will have a significant impact on the resin pressure and the quality of products.

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